

Original Research

The Role of Regulatory Quality in Optimizing the Impact of Oil Revenues on Economic Growth Process

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Received 19 February 2025 Revised 7 May 2025 Accepted 24 May 2025

Abstract

This study investigates the role of Regulatory Quality in the impact of oil revenues on economic growth for the countries of the Persian Gulf including Iran by applying a PSTR model from 2000 to 2023. Various studies on the relationship between oil revenues and economic growth have yielded mixed results, with few examining country-specific conditions, such as regulatory quality, in this context. In most of them, the non-linear relationships have not been considered. Thus, this paper examines the nonlinear association between oil revenues and economic growth. For this purpose, the paper uses the regulatory quality index, GDP growth, oil revenues, employment rate, size of government and capital formation. The results of model estimation reject the linearity hypothesis. Considering a transfer function with a threshold limit that represents a dual model is enough to define the nonlinear relationship between the studied variables and the quality of regulation considered as the transfer variable. The results show that the increase of oil revenues has a negative effect in the first regime and in the second regime has a positive effect on economic growth. It means that in a society with high quality of regulatory, increasing the oil revenues can improve economic growth. capital formation has a positive effect in both regimes. Employment rate has a negative effect in first regime and positive on the second one. the size of government has a negative effect on economic growth in both regimes.

Keywords: Economic development, oil income, Panel Smooth Transition Regression (PSTR), regulation.

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Introduction

The Persian Gulf has significant potential in terms of natural resources. It holds 60 percent of the world's proven oil reserves and accounts for 30 percent of global oil trade. The countries in this region have managed to generate substantial revenues through the sale of these resources. Therefore, it is expected that these countries would rank among the strong economies. However, what we observe today is that most of these countries have not been able to fully benefit from the blessings of these resources. This issue has attracted the attention of experts in this field to a group of countries that derive a significant portion of their income from oil exports and sales. As a result, many of them have sought to explain the factors influencing this relationship. In this context, many researchers have shown interest in examining the political conditions of these countries. While many studies have attempted to analyze how oil revenues impact the economic growth of oil-rich countries, there has been no theoretical discussion on this matter so far. Some research has indicated that oil revenues have a positive effect on economic growth, while others have emphasized their negative impact. Therefore, the impact of oil revenues on the economies of countries benefiting from these resources has faced many ambiguities. Countries whose economies are dominated by oil or other natural resources have specific characteristics that are not shared with industrial or developing economies. Although many economists, such as (Rostow, 1991) and (Nurkse, 1952), consider natural resources to be essential for the growth and development of countries, empirical observations from resource-rich countries contradict this theory, indicating poor economic performance in these nations. According to (Mirtorabi, 2008), the abundance of natural resources can act as both a blessing and a curse. It is considered a blessing in that an increase in the global price of a domestic resource raises total income, thereby facilitating consumption in the economy. Conversely, it is a curse because it can lead to the emergence of the Dutch disease, which imposes severe short-term and long-term effects on the economy. Some experts, such as (Luciani, 1986), have referred to oil as the "black curse." They believe that vast oil resources have increased the government's inclination to extract from this source quickly, immediately, and without concern, and the substantial profits resulting from this have led them into a state of euphoria. (Hashemi Miri et al., 2023) states that in resource-dependent countries, the rent from natural resources such as oil can have varying effects on economic growth. On one hand, it can provide the government with funding, facilitating increased public spending on infrastructure and leading to greater investment in machinery and equipment. On the other hand, it can create conditions for rising inflation through increased foreign reserves and liquidity. In response to rising inflation, the government tends to increase imports of tradable goods; however, this is not feasible for non-tradable goods, resulting in higher prices for this category of goods. In such circumstances, the return on investment in these goods generally exceeds that of the productive sector, leading individuals to prefer not to invest their capital in the industrial productive sector (manufacturing activities), which in turn causes economic stagnation and a decrease in economic growth. (Manasseh et al., 2018), also believe that the government's inability to reinvest the revenues from oil sales into the productive, industrial, and agricultural sectors slows the country's progress toward improving people's welfare. Therefore, it is expected that the increase in revenues from oil sales would reflect growth. However, evidence shows that these revenues have not had an impact on increasing growth. On the other hand, there are many studies that argue that natural resources such as oil and the revenue generated from its sale accelerate

the economic growth of the mentioned countries. For example, (Juselius, 1992), emphasized the existence of a long-term relationship between oil revenues and economic growth in a study. This is due to the fact that the oil sector plays a key role in boosting economic growth by stimulating non-oil sectors. In fact, as crude oil production increases, the share of the oil sector in the value-add created rises, which helps improve economic performance. The positive impact of oil revenues on economic growth leads to an increase in export income, which is allocated to construction costs, investment, and meeting the needs of domestic enterprises. This, in turn, results in an increase in national income, ultimately leading to higher economic growth (Cavalcanti et al., 2011).

Despite extensive studies conducted in this area, the way oil revenues affect economic growth remains ambiguous. Therefore, an important question is what factors cause oil revenues to stimulate the economic growth cycle in one country while acting as a barrier to achieving economic growth and progress in another country. This study aims to answer this key question and seeks to examine one of the important and influential conditions of countries in this regard, which is considering the role of regulatory quality. This is significant because the quality of regulations is one of the main tools of government intervention in the economy. This indicator is of particular importance due to its impact on how revenues are attracted or diverted, and as a measure of the quality of the laws enacted in the country. From an institutionalist perspective, the government and the market are complementary, and the government, as an inclusive institution, can define, establish, and institutionalize new institutions through legislation. Furthermore, by enacting appropriate laws, the government can play a significant role in creating the necessary infrastructure for the proper functioning of other institutions and the market's performance in the economy. Economists generally agree that the poor or favorable outcomes of any economic growth policy largely depend on the level of institutional quality in the economy (Sarmidi et al., 2014). With the inclusion of the significant factor of oil revenues in economic growth equations, the importance of high-quality institutions and the need for precise oversight with effective laws increase. According to (Matallah, 2020) enhancing the good governance capabilities of oil exporters in the Middle East and North Africa is the way out of the resource curse, as it can transform the wealth of oil into a blessing.

The Persian Gulf region, due to its heavy reliance on oil revenues, relatively similar economic structures, and significant differences in institutional quality and regulations, provides an ideal setting for analyzing the nonlinear effects of oil revenues on economic growth. This regional focus allows for the extraction of more precise policy recommendations that align with the shared characteristics of these countries.

Therefore, the following section will examine the literature on the role of supervision quality in the impact of oil revenues on economic growth, and relevant empirical studies on this topic will be reviewed. In the third section of this article, the panel smooth transition regression approach will be described, and the results obtained from estimating this model will be presented. Finally, conclusions and policy recommendations will be provided.

Previous Studies

(Abou-Ali & Abdelfattah, 2013), examined the relationship between resource abundance and economic growth for 62 countries during the period 1990-2007 using a simultaneous equations model. Their results revealed the existence of a negative relationship between resource abundance and economic growth.

(Alssadek & Benhin, 2021), in their study conducted for 36 developed and developing oil-rich countries, examined the hypothesis of the existence of Dutch disease. The results of this study showed that oil revenues increase the real exchange rate and reduce output. There is also a significant difference in the effects of oil revenues on the real exchange rate and output across countries, which is likely due to differences in the level of institutional quality and economic policy.

(Jalilian et al., 2007) studied the impact of oil revenue on inflation and growth rates for Iran. Their results proved that oil revenue only has a slow direct effect on growth. has tested the hypothesis that the efficiency and quality of regulation affect the economic performance of an economy. Two proxies for regulatory effectiveness were included separately and then combined as determinants of economic growth performance, using both cross-sectional and panel data methods. The results from both sets of modeling suggest a strong causal link between regulatory quality and economic growth and confirm that the standard of regulation matters for economic performance.

(Silberberger & Königer, 2016) examined the relationship between trade and regulatory quality and economic growth for 106 countries. they find that, although trade is also significant, regulatory quality, has a bigger and highly significant, nonlinear, positive impact on economic growth.

(Lee et al., 2021) in their study, investigated the relationship between financial systems, regulatory quality, and economic growth for nine selected African countries. This study shows that the quality of regulation plays an important role in the finance-growth nexus as it has a mediating effect on both the real and financial sectors.

(Farhadi et al., 2015) examined the effect of resource rent on economic freedom using the GMM method for 99 countries during the years 1970-2010. Their results showed that oil revenues have a positive effect on economic freedom, meaning that their empirical findings do not support the resource curse hypothesis.

(Maleki, 2018), studied the short-term and long-term effects of oil revenues on economic poverty in urban areas in Iran. The main finding of this study shows that in the long run, each one percent increase (decrease) in oil revenues causes a 1.43 percent increase (decrease) in the economic poverty rate of urban households. This result is in line with economic theories regarding the relationship between oil revenues and poverty in developing countries.

(Manasseh et al., 2023), in a study they conducted for Nigeria, examined the impact of foreign direct investment and oil revenue on economic growth during the years 1991-2019. Their empirical findings showed that foreign direct investment and oil revenue significantly affected growth.

(Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2013), in a study conducted for Nigeria, showed that the quality of the country's economic institutions has been severely negatively affected by oil revenues. They propose direct distribution of oil revenues among the people as a solution to this problem.

(Stevens, 2003), considers the mechanism of the impact of natural resource abundance on economic growth as one of the channels of long-term decline in the relationship between Dutch disease, the substitution effect, and increased government intervention in the economy.

(Tiba, 2019), in a study examined the effect of natural resource abundance on economic growth in oil-exporting countries using the PSTR model. The results of this study indicate the nonlinearity of the relationship between oil revenues and economic growth, as well as the hypothesis of the existence of a resource curse.

A review of previous literature shows that the impact of oil revenues on economic growth is accompanied by mixed results. Previous studies have examined the role of institutions in this regard, but the prominent role of regulatory quality has not been independently and nonlinearly examined so far. It is expected that over time and at different levels of regulatory quality, the coefficients and the way oil revenues affect economic growth will change. So, this study has taken a further step to solve the problem through panel smooth Transition Regression, as the most prominent model of regime-switching to consider the relationship between nonlinear and threshold between two variables. Also, it is essential to point that in PSTR model due to adjustment parameter and threshold variable observations, over the time the estimated coefficient would change in different levels.

Theoretical Framework and the model

Growth Models

Since the study of development issues in countries around the world became a topic of interest to economists, economic growth has gained general acceptance as the best indicator of a country's economic development. In fact, it should be said that the theory of growth goes back to David Hume, who believed in free trade with emphasis on the greater contribution of people, industrial producers and farmers. While Hume's main growth equation was capital formation and trade expansion, his student Adam Smith's growth equation was based on the three factors of land, capital and work force. Later, in the book of principles of Economics, Marshall reviewed his growth model with emphasis on the determinants of income distribution and the variables of the savings rate and work force efficiency. Keynes, in response to the conditions of economic recession in 1929-1930 that engulfed the capitalist world, proposed his theory to transform economic stagnation into prosperity in 1936. He also stressed the need for government intervention in the economy, as did some of the new classics. From Keynes's perspective, what will happen to the economy in the long run as a result of applying this policy is not an important issue, he thinks about the economy that is being destroyed (Barro, 2000). After that, Solow presented his growth model in the 1950s. He considered technology to be the engine of economic growth and in his model. he analyzed production behavior based on

variables such as physical capital and labor. In the late 1980s, another group of economic thinkers, including Romer (1986) and Lucas (1986), introduced the discussion of ideas, knowledge, and human capital into growth models and presented models that became known as endogenous growth models. With the introduction of human capital into growth models, its explanatory power increased, which made the cause of the difference in per capita income of countries more justifiable, but nevertheless there were still some flaws in these models (Mokhtari et al., 2021). During the years when classical thinkers were focused on perfecting their growth models, other thinkers were also trying to provide an explanation of the causes of economic growth. Among these efforts, the paradigm that seemed to take the lead was the new institutional economics. Accordingly, development is the result of a specific type of institution that currently exists in only 15-20% of countries in the world, and this specific type of institution is more than a matter of one or a few specific institutions. (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2010) believe that economic institutions are important for economic growth because they shape the motivation of key economic actors. In fact, they specifically affect investment in physical, human, technological resources, as well as production organizations. Institutions and institutional economics have attracted many supporters among economic thinkers and other scientists in explaining the causes of income differences between countries, the differences in different levels of growth and development. Institutional economics has been proposed as a complement and remedy for some of the weaknesses of previous schools. The type of institutions existing in society is important, and only the existence of good institutions can lead to growth and development.

Oil revenues and Growth

The significant increase in oil prices in global markets over the past years has drawn researchers' attention to the revenues generated from it and the effects and consequences of these revenues on the economies of countries rich in these resources. Therefore, oil revenues and the manner in which they flow into economic arteries are among the challenging topics in the field of economics. Initially, there was the belief that the abundant revenues generated from natural resources would create wealth for a country, leading to economic progress and a reduction in poverty. However, over time, empirical observations in many countries have contradicted this claim. (Seghir & Damette, 2013), examined the relationship between oil revenues and economic growth, stating that as income from the sale of natural resources increases, followed by an increase in government spending, the overall demand in the economy rises. Consequently, the productivity of economic activities in the commercial, services, and housing sectors increases compared to the industrial and agricultural sectors, leading to an imbalance between the economic sectors of the country and a shift in the share of factors from the productive sector to the non-productive sector. In such a situation, given the higher productivity of the commercial, services, and housing sectors compared to others, the liberalization of banking rates and their increase in the short term causes these sectors to attract more financial resources, resulting in a relative recession in the industrial sector and especially in agriculture. In this context, countries with a high degree of dependence on resource rents lack a critical level of human capital necessary for a sustainable transition to a knowledge-based economy, and as a result, they are prone to increasing poverty and widening income gaps between the rich and the poor (Farzanegan & Habibpour, 2017). According to (Elmi & Jahadi, 2011), since oil revenues are one of the

most important sources of financing the government budget in oil-exporting countries, changes in these revenues are expected to affect the government budget. In addition, in countries where governments consider themselves the owners of large oil revenues and there is weak supervision over their performance, huge oil rents are also benefited. As a result, rent-seeking tendencies in these countries not only delay economic growth but also lead to strengthening the public sector and weakening the private sector. (Sachs & Warner, 2001) believe that countries with large natural resources struggle with low and sometimes negative economic growth. (Rodriguez, 2006), in his article, states that the abundance of natural resources can act as a blessing or a curse. A blessing in that the discovery of natural resources increases the global price of a domestic resource, leading to increased income and subsequent consumption in the economy, and a curse that causes the economy to suffer from Dutch disease. Therefore, the way these resources function varies across countries.

Some articles look at this issue from the perspective of institutional economics and state that natural resources such as oil have an adverse effect on the institutions of oil-exporting countries and thus affect the economic performance of these countries. The existence of weak institutions causes the rents from resources to be easily obtained by rent-seeking individuals through these institutions and there is no fair distribution among the people of the society. Economists such as Torvik also consider the poor quality of the institutions in the country to be the only reason for low economic growth in countries rich in natural resources (Rahmani & Golestani, 2010). (Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2013) also examined this issue in an article about Nigeria and showed that the quality of the country's economic institutions has been severely negatively affected by oil revenues. They suggest the direct distribution of oil revenues among the people as a solution to this problem.

(Alssadek & Benhin, 2021), in their study conducted for 36 developed and developing oil-rich countries, examined the hypothesis of the existence of Dutch disease. The results of this study showed that oil revenues increase the real exchange rate and reduce output. They also found that the impact of oil revenues on production and the real exchange rate varies across these countries, stating that these differences are likely due to the different institutional structures and economic policies of these countries.

Therefore, the economic effects of natural resources have been different in different periods of history and in different countries, but the number of countries that have not been able to manage these resources due to their weak economic and legal structures is greater (Ploeg, 2006).

Economic Regulation Theory

The role of an effective regulatory regime in promoting economic growth and development has generated considerable interest among researchers and practitioners in recent years (World Bank, 2001). The intention of this indicator is to measure the government's ability to formulate and implement policies and regulations that expand the presence and activities of the private sector. A greater presence of the private sector as a result of the implementation of government-designed policies indicates better governance. More broadly, the quality of regulations indicator reflects the level of

transparency, efficiency of laws and regulations, and oversight of their implementation, as well as the level of existing bureaucracy. Regulation can take many forms and the form of regulation policy adopted in developing countries has shifted over time (Minogue, 2005). From the 1960s to the 1980s, market failure was used to legitimize direct government involvement in productive activities in developing countries, by promoting industrialization through import substitution, investing directly in industry and agriculture, and by extending public ownership of enterprises. However, following the apparent success of market liberalization programs in some developed countries, and the evidence of the failure of state-led economic planning in developing ones (World Bank, 1995), the role of state regulation was redefined and narrowed to that of ensuring an undistorted policy environment in which efficient markets could operate. Deregulation was widely adopted, often as part of structural adjustment programs, with the aim of reducing the “regulatory burden” on the market economy (Jalilian et al., 2007). In the past 20 years the role of a good regulatory framework for a country’s development has been emphasized by policy makers, researchers and international organizations alike. The regulations of a country are part of its economic institutions, which – in turn – are shaped by the political institutions (Robinson & Acemoglu, 2012). Building effective regulatory structures in developing countries is not simply an issue of the technical design of the regulatory instruments, it is also concerned with the quality of supporting regulatory institutions and capacity (Mokhtarifar et al., 2023). (Demetriades & Andrianova, 2004) argue that competent and honest regulatory quality not only can productively mobilize human and physical resources in an economy but also leads to economic development because such quality mediates and signifies the momentum of economic growth. the capacity of the state to provide strong regulatory institutions will be an important determinant of how well markets perform. An economy with a developed institutional capacity is more likely to be able to design and implement effective regulation, which should contribute to an improved economic growth. Weaknesses in institutional capacity to deliver “good” regulation may be predicted to affect economic development adversely (Jalilian et al., 2007).

PSTR Model

In this section, the panel smooth transition regression model (PSTR) is explaining and the estimates are presenting. (González et al., 2005) are specified a PSTR model with two extreme regimes and one transition function following:

$$y_{it} = \mu_i + \beta'_0 x_{it} + \beta'_1 x_{it} (q_{it}; \gamma, c) + u_{it} \quad i = 1, \dots, N, t = 1, \dots, T \quad (1)$$

Where N and T denote the cross-section and time dimensions of the panel, respectively. The dependent variable y_{it} is a scalar x_{it} is a k -dimensional vector of time-varying exogenous variables μ_i represents the fixed individual effect, and u_{it} are the errors. Transition function $g(q_{it}; \gamma, c)$ is a continuous function of the observable variable q_{it} and is normalized to be bounded between 0 and 1, and these extreme values are associated with regression coefficients β_0 and $\beta_0 + \beta_1$. Wich represent the coefficients associated with the explanatory variables in the linear and in the nonlinear regimes respectively. γ is the transition or slope parameter, describing the slope of the transition function. C is the location parameter.

A smooth transfer mechanism can be modeled using various transfer functions, provided that these functions are continuous and have a calculable integral. We follow (González et al., 2005) by using the logistic specification

$$g(q_{it}; \gamma, c) = \left[1 + \exp(-\gamma \prod_{j=1}^m (q_{it} - c_j)) \right]^{-1}, \quad \gamma > 0, c_1 \leq c_2 \leq \dots \leq c_m \quad (2)$$

Where $c = (c_1, \dots, c_m)$ is an m -dimensional vector of location parameters and the slope parameter γ determines the smoothness of the transitions. The restrictions $\gamma > 0$ and $c_1 \leq c_2 \leq \dots \leq c_m$ are imposed for identification purposes.

A generalization of the PSTR model to allow for more than two different regimes is the additive model.

$$y_{it} = \mu_i + \beta'_0 x_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^r \beta'_j x_{it} g_j(q_{it}; \gamma_j, c_j) + u_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where the transition functions $g_j(q_{it}; \gamma_j, c_j)$, $j = 1, \dots, r$, are of the logistic type (2). If $m = 1$, $q_{it}^j = q_{it}$ and $\gamma_j \rightarrow \infty$ for all $j = 1, \dots, r$, the model in (3) becomes a PTR model with $r + 1$ regimes.

(González et al., 2005) suggest in practice it is usually sufficient to consider $m = 1$ or $m = 2$, as these values allow for commonly encountered types of variation in the parameters. For $m = 1$, the model implies that the two extreme regimes are associated with low and high values of q_{it} with a single monotonic transition of the coefficients from β_0 to $\beta_0 + \beta_1$ as q_{it} increases, where the change is centred around c_1 . When $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, $g(q_{it}; \gamma, c)$ becomes an indicator function $I[q_{it} > c_1]$, defined as $I[A] = 1$ when the event A occurs and 0 otherwise. In that case the PSTR model in (1) reduces to the two-regime panel threshold model of (Hansen, 1999). For $m = 2$, the transition function has its minimum at $(c_1 + c_2)/2$ and attains the value 1 both at low and high values of q_{it} . When $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, the model becomes a three-regime threshold model whose outer regimes are identical and different from the middle regime. In general, when $m > 1$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, the number of distinct regimes remains two, with the transition function switching back and forth between zero and one at c_1, \dots, c_m . Finally, for any value of m the transition function (2) becomes constant when $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, in which case the model collapses into a homogenous or linear panel regression model with fixed effects.

Estimating the parameters in the PSTR model (1) is a relatively straightforward application of the fixed effects estimator and nonlinear least squares (NLS) that this estimation procedure is equivalent to maximum likelihood (ML) and first is eliminated the individual effects by removing individual-specific means and then is applied NLS to the transformed data (González et al., 2005). But according to studies by (Fok et al., 2005), (González et al., 2005) and (Colletaz & Hurlin, 2006) in estimation PSTR model, first testing linearity against the PSTR done and while the null hypothesis is rejected, must specify the number of transition functions to nonlinear behavior between selected variables. For this purpose, the null hypothesis of the existence of one transition function is tested against the hypothesis that there are at least two transition functions. If the null hypothesis is not rejected, including one transition function will suffice to examine the nonlinear relationships among variables. However, if the null hypothesis is rejected, there

will be at least two transition function of the PSTR model and in continuing should be tested the null hypothesis of the existence of two transition functions that there are at least three transition functions. This process should continue until the null hypothesis is accepted.

Testing the linearity can be done by testing $H_0: \gamma=0$ or $H_0: \beta_1=0$. But in both cases, the test will be non-standard since under H_0 the PSTR model contains unidentified nuisance parameters as it was the case in the Hansen s PTR model. This issue is well known in the literature devoted to the time series threshold models (Hansen, 1996). However, in the context of the PSTR model, Gonzalez, (Teräsvirta, 1996) present an original solution similar to the solution proposed by (Luukkonen et al., 1988) for time series models. It consists to replace the transition function $g_j(q_{it}; \gamma, c_j)$ by its first-order Taylor expansion around $\gamma=0$. After reparameterization, this leads to the auxiliary regression

$$y_{it} = \mu_i + \beta_0^* x_{it} + \beta_1^* x_{it} q_{it} + \dots + \beta_m^* x_{it} q_{it}^m + u_{it}^* \quad (4)$$

Under the equation (4) null linearity hypothesis becomes to $H^*0 : \beta^*_1 = \dots = \beta^*_m = 0$ that rejection of the null hypothesis means that the relationship is non-linear and its non rejection suggests the linear model specification. To test this hypothesis according to study of (Colletaz & Hurlin, 2006) use from three statistics LM_w , LM_F and LR that are calculated by the following equations:

$$LM_w = \frac{TN(SSR_0 - SSR_1)}{SSR_0} \quad (5)$$

$$LM_F = \frac{(SSR_0 - SSR_1)/km}{\left[\frac{SSR_0}{TN - N - mk} \right]} \quad (6)$$

$$LR = -2[\log(SSR_1) - \log(SSR_0)] \quad (7)$$

In the above equations SSR_0 , is the linear panel sum of squared residuals SSR_1 and is the sum of squared residuals of the nonlinear PSTR model. Also, T , N , K and m denote time period, cross-section number, explanatory variables number and location parameters number respectively. In Testing the hypothesis of no remaining heterogeneity, choose a first-order Taylor approximation and it leads to the auxiliary regression.

$$y_{it} = \mu_i + \beta^*_0 x_{it} + \beta^*_1 x_{it} g(q_{it}; \hat{Y}_1, \hat{c}_1) + \beta^*_2 x_{it} q_{it} + \dots + \beta^*_m x_{it} q_{it}^m + u_{it}^* \quad (8)$$

Where \hat{Y}_1 and \hat{c}_1 are estimates under the null hypothesis. The hypothesis of no remaining heterogeneity can then be restated as $H^*0 : \beta^*_{21} = \dots = \beta^*_{2m} = 0$.

Data and PSTR Results

This study investigates the threshold effects of oil revenues on economic growth in oil-rich countries of the Persian Gulf including Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Emirates, Qatar and Bahrain for the period of 2000-2023, using Panel Smooth Transition Regression (PSTR) model. The data used in this study were collected from the

WDI website. Also, the regulatory quality dimension of institutional quality provided in the World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) serves as our measure of quality of regulations (RQ). It ranges approximately from -2.5 to +2.5 and reflects perceptions of the government’s ability to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations. Data for some indicators were incomplete for a year or two for one or two countries; in these cases, a three-year moving average method was used to estimate the missing values in order to avoid deleting observations and reducing the sample size. The econometric model used in this study is derived from the (Tiba, 2019) and in a general case of PSTR model that provided in equation (3), can be specified as follows1:

$$\text{Grit} = \mu_i + \alpha_0 (\text{Or})_{it} + \alpha_1 (\text{K})_{it} + \alpha_2 (\text{L})_{it} + \alpha_3 (\text{Gs})_{it} + \{ \beta_0 (\text{Or})_{it} + \beta_1 (\text{K})_{it} + \beta_2 (\text{L})_{it} + \beta_3 (\text{Gs})_{it} \} F(\text{qit}; \gamma, c) + \text{uit} \quad (9)$$

where Gr, Or, K, L and Gs, are the growth rate of real per capita GDP, Oil Rent, gross capital formation, Employment in industry and General government final consumption expenditure. The transition function $g(\text{qit}; \gamma, c)$ is continuous in the observable transition variable. The variables added to the model follow the growth empirics literature, such as (Dada & Abanikanda, 2019) and (Seghir & Damette, 2013).

In this model, the first threshold regime corresponds to the case where the regulatory quality level is lower than its threshold value (0.2846), and the second threshold regime represents the case where the regulatory quality level has crossed the threshold and is above it. The transition between these two regimes is also accomplished by a transfer function. This function considers values close to 0 for levels below the threshold and values close to 1 for levels above the threshold. The threshold value is not pre-assigned but is endogenously estimated through the PSTR procedure. This threshold is common to all cross-sectional units, enabling a unified classification of observations into low-and high- regulatory quality regimes.

Before the estimating of PSTR model, it is necessary stationary testing be performed on variables. In this study, (Levin et al., 2002) unit root test is used. The results of this test, as table (1) shows, indicate that all the variables are stationary in the studied period.

Table 1. LLC Test for Unit Root

		variables					
		Gr	RQ	Or	K	L	Gs
LLC test	T-statistic	-2.5607	-4.6898	-2.0889	-3.0735	-1.4647	-5.7592
	prob	0.005	0.000	0.003	0.001	0.000	0.000

As was discussed in the previous section, first linearity hypothesis has been tested against hypothesis of the existence of PSTR model with consideration of regulatory quality index as a transition variable. According to the results in Table (2), all statistics for one threshold values reject linearity hypothesis and show nonlinear relationship between variables. After ensuring the nonlinear relationship between variables, to determine the number of transition function, next step is that to be investigated the hypothesis of no remaining heterogeneity. According to the results in Table (2), only existence of one transition function will suffice to explanation the nonlinear relationship between oil revenues and economic growth.

Table 2. Tests for Linearity and No Remaining Nonlinearity

	M=1			M=2		
	LM _w	LMF	LR	LM _w	LMF	LR
H ₀ : r=0 H ₁ : r=1	13.966 (0.007)	3.530 (0.008)	14.500 (0.000)	21.377 (0.006)	2.756 (0.007)	22.663 (0.000)
H ₀ : r=1 H ₁ : r=2	3.142 (0.534)	0.715 (0.583)	3.168 (0.530)	2.949 (0.938)	0.328 (0.955)	2.972 (0.936)

Notes: m is the number of location parameters and r is the number of transition functions. The corresponding p-values are reported in brackets.

After were rejected the linear relationship among the variables under consideration and was selected one transition function, then the number of location parameters should be selected for the final model. For this purpose and to follow (Colletaz & Hurlin, 2006) and (Eggosh.C, 2010), two PSTR models is estimated with one and two threshold values and the sum of squared residuals, Akaike information criterion and Schwars is calculated for each of them.

In Table 3 the mentioned criteria for both PSTR, models were presented. Even though there is some difference in the calculated results of criteria, all three of them suggest a better model in terms of a threshold value. Thus, a PSTR model with one transition function and one threshold value is selected to investigate the nonlinear behavior of the studied variables.

Table 3. Determination of the Number of Location Parameters

	RSS	Schwarz Criterion	AIC Criterion
M=1	1.6077	18.6089	18.4223
M=2	1.6436	18.6093	18.4284

After PSTR model with one transition function and one threshold value was selected that meaning a two-regime model, the model is estimated in the following that its results are given in Table (4).

Table 4. Parameter's Estimates for Final PSTR Models

Or	coefficients	K	coefficients	L coefficients	Gs coefficients		
α_0	-0.1522 (-2.3100)	β_0	1.6956 (2.5215)	θ_0	-0.0469 (-0.2056)	δ_0	-0.0427 (-2.2657)
α_1	0.5748 (3.2528)	β_1	1.9105 (2.2333)	θ_1	0.5840 (3.1752)	δ_1	-0.5521 (-3.4084)
1 st regime: dlyit = $\mu_i - 0.1522 \text{ Orit} + 1.6956 \text{ Kit} - 0.0469 \text{ Lit} - 0.0427 \text{ Gsit}$				G(qit ; γ, c)=0			
2 nd regime: dlyit = $\mu_i + 0.5748 \text{ Orit} + 1.9105 \text{ Kit} + 0.5840 \text{ Lit} - 0.5521 \text{ Gsit}$				G(qit ; γ, c)=1			
$\gamma = 7.0738$				$c = 0.2846$			

Notes: The values in brackets are the T-statistic. γ and c are the Slope and Location Parameters respectively.

Table 4 shows the estimated results and based on slope parameter which represents the adjustment speed from one regime to other, is the same as the adjustment speed of 7.0738. The location of regime modification has been estimated 0.2846, so if the index of regulatory quality exceeds the 0.2846, the behavior of variables will be as a second regime and if it be lower the above-mentioned threshold, it will be as first regime. Since the variables coefficients modifies based on transition variable and slope parameter and through the time is not equal for different countries, it is not impossible to directly interpret the coefficients score and just the signs should be analyzed.

Table 5 shows the five countries under study, categorized by regime and based on a threshold value. In this table, countries with regulatory quality lower than the threshold value are placed in the first regime, and the remaining countries are placed in the second regime.

Table 5 Country separation based on average Regulatory Quality Index

Country	Average regulatory quality	Regime classification
Bahrain	0.6977	High-quality
Iran	-1.4609	Low-quality
Iraq	-1.2877	Low-quality
Kuwait	0.1394	Low-quality
Oman	0.4810	High-quality
Qatar	0.5498	High-quality
Saudi Arabia	0.0881	Low-quality
United Arab Emirates	0.7997	High-quality

Clearly this result indicates the asymmetric relationship of oil rent and economic growth in different levels of regulatory quality. Employment variables have negative impact in first regime and positive impact on second regime on economic growth. The size of government has a negative effect on economic growth in both regimes. Also, the gross capital formation variable in both regimes has a positive impact on economic growth. which indicates that gross capital formation acts as an encouragement of economic growth in this Countries.

As it was discussed before, two considered cases were part of extreme regimes and act between two regimes, so the numerical value of the variables coefficients in extreme states cannot be interpreted; To explain the matter it's better to note that the variables coefficients are not equal and based on transition variable and the slope parameter they are changed. To achieve this feature of PSTR model, the estimated coefficients in each variable based on transition variable and the slope parameter were calculated and drawn in diagrams 1 to 4.

Diagram 1 shows that if the quality of regulatory index is below its threshold value, an increase in oil revenues leads to a decrease in economic growth. Conversely, if this index is above the threshold, oil revenues have a positive impact on economic growth. In interpreting these results, which align with findings from other studies such as (Tiba, 2019), it can be stated that in countries with low governance quality, governments are unable to effectively manage oil resources. Consequently, in such countries, oil revenues

may be allocated to specific groups or government entities instead of being invested in capital projects, leading to widespread corruption. On the other hand, in the absence of strong and precise oversight, financial resources and oil revenues are directed towards unproductive projects, eliminating opportunities for infrastructure investments. In contrast, in countries with high governance quality, the government can manage oil revenues effectively. The presence of a transparent and efficient oversight system prevents corruption and facilitates the allocation of resources to productive sectors. Additionally, in such countries, these revenues can become catalysts for sustainable growth, infrastructure development, and strengthening non-oil sectors. Furthermore, strong oversight enables governments to guide the economy towards stability through appropriate monetary and fiscal policies in the event of falling oil prices, thereby preventing economic crises. As a result of this discussion, it can be said that when the regulatory institutions of a country operate effectively, oil revenues can become a tool for sustainable economic development and a reduction in dependence on natural resources. Conversely, weak and inefficient oversight can lead to corruption, resource wastage, and increased reliance on oil, which threatens economic growth. Therefore, strengthening the quality of oversight and transparency in the management of oil revenues is key to creating a suitable environment for economic growth and prosperity.

The way Gross Capital Formation affect GDP growth has been shown in diagram 2. According to this diagram Capital accumulation in both regimes have a positive impact on economic growth, which increases as we move towards the second regime. This finding is consistent with studies such as those by (Mokhtarifar et al., 2023) and (Hashemi Miri et al., 2023). Capital formation is considered as a prime determinant of economic development in any economy. Increasing capital formation increases production. High regulatory quality index is one of the factors affecting investors' decisions. It can be said that high-quality oversight contributes to creating a secure and predictable environment for investment, which ultimately allows capital accumulation to be utilized more effectively in enhancing productivity and economic growth.

In the third chart, the coefficients of the employment variable are plotted against the transfer variable. This chart shows that if the quality of regulation is high in a country, an increase in the level of employment has a positive impact on economic growth. In interpreting these results, it can be stated that high regulatory quality improves the business environment, creates conditions for attracting investment, and effectively regulates the labor market. In systems with high regulatory quality, governments are able to establish effective supportive frameworks for employment-generating sectors and prevent the diversion of resources to unproductive sectors. Under such conditions, the workforce is attracted more effectively to the labor market, leading to increased production and economic growth. This result is also consistent with studies conducted in this area, such as (Doerr et al., 2024).

Finally diagram 4 deals on the negative influence of government size on economic growth and after going over threshold and entering to second regime the amount of influence increase. In interpreting these results, it can be said that the large size of government leads to reduced competition, increased taxes, administrative complexities, and higher administrative costs. In fact, a large government takes resources from the private sector and reduces economic efficiency by creating monopolies or unnecessary

interventions in the markets, thereby generally limiting economic growth. Additionally, a large government may result in the allocation of resources to low-yield paths and increase opportunity costs for the private sector. Governments that engage more extensively in the economy tend to spend significant time and resources on matters that may not be profitable in the long run, rather than focusing on infrastructure or economic policy-making. Furthermore, a larger government can act as a barrier to innovation and entrepreneurship in the private sector. Particularly in sectors where the government intervenes directly, less competition is generated, and motivation in the private sector diminishes. This finding is also consistent with studies such as that of (Skinner, 1991).

Diagram 1

Diagram 2

Diagram 3

Diagram 4

Conclusions

The present study has considered the threshold effects of oil revenues on economic growth in oil-rich countries of the Persian Gulf including Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Emirates, Qatar and Bahrain for the period of 2000-2023. To do this work, the Panel Smooth Transition Regression (PSTR) was used which developed by (Fok et al., 2005), (González et al., 2005), (Colletaz & Hurlin, 2006). PSTR model as an outstanding regime-switching model not only does not impose any limiting and specific function on the relationship of variables but also the probable nonlinear relationship between variables are continuously modeled through transition function based on threshold variable observations. Also, in this model heterogeneous of estimated parameters with coefficients modifications for different countries are solved through time. The estimated results confirm the nonlinear relationship of variables between oil revenues and economic growth and it is sufficient to consider a transition function with a threshold for accelerating nonlinear behavior. The estimated results of PSTR model show that when the regulatory quality index exceeds the 0.2846, the regime changes will occur. The slope parameter which represents the adjustment speed from one regime to another is estimated 7.0738.

The estimated coefficients results of variables considered in the model show that under conditions of low regulatory quality, oil revenues have a negative impact on economic growth, while at higher levels of regulatory quality, oil revenues have a positive impact on economic growth. These results indicate that simply possessing oil resources is not sufficient for economic growth; rather, the effective utilization of these resources requires a suitable institutional framework and high-quality policymaking and economic regulation to ensure that these resources are used correctly and efficiently. In the Gulf Persian countries, which generally have economies highly dependent on oil revenues and diverse institutional structures, the quality of regulations has a significant impact on directing the effect of oil revenues on economic growth. In countries with stronger regulatory institutions and more transparent regulatory frameworks, oil revenues have been able to contribute to sustainable economic growth; however, in countries with lower quality regulations, these resources have more often led to inefficiency and economic volatility. Therefore, in these countries, to optimally utilize oil resources, strengthening institutional capacity, particularly in the areas of regulatory, budgetary transparency, and corruption control, appears essential. Although gross capital formation variable in both regimes has a positive impact on economic growth. Employment rate has a negative effect in first regime and positive on the second one. Also, the size of government has a negative effect on economic growth in both regimes.

The results of this research can serve as a model for other oil-rich regions around the world to reform institutional structures, improve the quality of regulations and transparency, and enhance adopted policies.

Generally, according to the results of PSTR model can be concluded that:

1. The government can prevent abuse and corruption by strengthening internal oversight institutions and creating transparency in executive processes.

2. Oil revenues should be invested through transparent financial policies and proper management in various sectors of the economy, especially in infrastructure, education, and healthcare. The government can help reduce corruption and waste of resources by improving the quality of oversight.

3. Allocating a portion of oil revenues to infrastructure and industrial projects that strengthen the private sector can lead to growth and job creation. The government can support the private sector by closely monitoring the implementation of these projects and ensuring transparency in the bidding and contracting processes.

4. The government can enhance the quality of oversight and the efficiency of using oil revenues by training and empowering employees in the management of natural and financial resources.

5. Policymakers should seek to diversify the country's revenue sources. Utilizing oil revenues for the development of non-oil sectors, such as domestic industries and agriculture, can contribute to sustainable economic growth.

Funding

This study received no financial support from any organization.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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